

CULTiVATE

Food Sharing Landscapes in CULTIVATE Hub Locations: Utrecht City Profile

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UTRECHT CITY PROFILE

Geography and Economy

Situated in the centre of the Netherlands, Utrecht City is traversed by four rivers: Kromme Rijn, Oude Rijn, Vecht River, and the Amsterdam-Rijn Canal. The rivers are connected by three canals built in the 12th century¹. Utrecht City is the 4th largest city in the Netherlands and the capital of Utrecht Province. In 2019, the Utrecht Province recorded a population of 1.38 million people, making up 8% of the Dutch population². Utrecht City is home to 352,941 inhabitants who live at a density of 3,921 persons per square kilometre. Utrecht City is also an important hub for internal and international travel³. The City of Utrecht is part of the Randstad conurbation, a socio-economic region that holds political and cultural importance at the national level⁴. The Randstad region generates 46% of the total Dutch GDP and Utrecht Province records the second-highest GDP per capita in the area⁵. The contribution of the agricultural sector to the Utrecht Province's economy remains low, accounting for only 0.5%, whereas tertiary sectors such as finance, education and trade remain the main contributors to the local economy at 87%, followed by industry and construction 12.5%². The top 3 most important economic sectors in the City of Utrecht are: business services; government, education and care; trade and hospitality, closely followed by culture, recreation and other services. Utrecht City municipality records an unemployment rate of 3.3%. According to the municipal statistics, 64.6% of the total Utrecht population are active in employment, including self-employment⁶. At the regional level, 93% of Utrecht Province residents use the internet daily for purchasing goods and services including Internet banking, and 74% maintain a presence on social networks⁷. In terms of technology and innovation, Utrecht city hosts the largest science park in the Netherlands, with ten knowledge institutions and 130 R&D companies⁸.

Politics and Society

The political system of the Netherlands is a parliamentary constitutional monarchy. The government consists of the King, the Prime Minister, and the ministers. The parliament has two chambers, one of which (Tweede Kamer- Lower Chamber) is elected directly by Dutch citizens⁹. The electoral system works based on a list system of political representation, with elections being held for the three different levels of governance: national parliament, provincial councils, regional water authorities and municipal councils¹⁰. Administratively, the Netherlands is organized into twelve provinces, each with its own representative body and government. The provincial governments form the layer between the central government and the 342 municipalities. The provincial governments oversee matters such as spatial planning in rural areas, regional accessibility and regional economic policy. Municipal governments are elected by Dutch and EU citizens registered in the municipality; non-EU nationals are excluded from voting unless they have been living in the country for more than five years¹¹. Municipal governments draft local regulations and budget allocations in line with national policy and national strategies for environmental management. The city of Utrecht has a high level of cultural diversity being home to 172 nationalities. Almost 40% of the residents are either first or second-generation migrants. This contributes to a vibrant and dynamic cultural life¹¹. The Province of Utrecht has one of the highest-educated population in the Netherlands¹². In the city of Utrecht alone, more than half the registered residents have a university diploma.

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Food and Food Culture

In Utrecht Province, most of the agricultural land is used as grasslands and dairy production. Fruit and vegetable production accounts for an insignificant share of food produced in the region. An FAO report, which includes Utrecht City and neighbouring municipalities, found that the agricultural landscape is made up of small-scale farms and gardens with an average farm size of 4 hectares¹³. Farms in Utrecht City often provide non-agricultural services such as biodiversity conservation and enhancement as well as educational activities and labour integration programs with the latter being recognized as ‘zorgborderij’ (care farms)¹⁴. For example, Utrecht Natuurlijk, a network organization of 11 community gardens and farms in Utrecht City, created a nature-based educational curriculum for school children, which is implemented by nature educators at the city farm locations every year¹⁵. In 2022, 8 out of 10 Utrechters reported purchasing organic and fair-trade products and excluding meat from their daily meals³. Utrecht’s food culture is diverse and linked with the Netherlands’ colonial history and patterns of migration¹⁶. Within Utrecht, food governance falls under the jurisdiction of several departments including the Public Health Team, Climate and Circular Economy and the Green Department. Since 2007 Utrecht city is involved in the Fairtrade municipality movement¹⁷. At the Milan Expo in 2015, Utrecht municipality signed the Milan Urban Food Pact Policy, and is one of the six project pilot cities committed to improving food systems based on the principle of sustainability and social justice¹⁸. Currently, in the city of Utrecht, 2% of residents are considered to be underweight, while more than 8% are considered obese¹⁹. In a survey conducted by Meetellen on healthy eating, 22% of respondents of those which are considered vulnerable identified price as a major barrier for healthy eating²⁰. Around 14% of the Utrecht population finds itself at or below the poverty line and food banks in the city report distributing around 600 packages a week to help families make ends meet²⁰. Moreover, an underlying policy document that concerns food is the Utrecht Food Agenda identifying six underlying principles to make the city’s food system more sustainable in line with the UN’s Sustainable Development Goals²⁰. The key areas of work focus on promoting awareness, healthy and integrated supply, rural-urban connectedness, circularity, and edible city landscapes²¹. Utrecht municipality commits to halve the amount of food waste as recorded in 2020 by 2030²¹. Furthermore, to expand the share of food grown in the city, Utrecht is championing ‘edible district’ projects creating edible green spaces and encouraging residents to maintain it and harvest from it²².

Environment and Sustainability

A key environmental policy instrument in Utrecht is the Green Structure Plan 2017-2030²³ which includes subsidising the installation of green roofs in the city with a total of 1,808 m³ of biodiverse green roofs subsidized by 2022^{24, 25}. In 2022, Utrecht received the European Prize for European Public Space²⁶. In 2016, Utrecht Municipality declared itself a ‘Global Goal City’, with the promise to align its policies with the UN Sustainable Development Goals framework²¹. By 2040, Utrecht City’s population is expected to increase to up to 470,000 inhabitants. To accommodate the new inhabitants, the municipality is planning to build over 49,000 homes in the next 20 years³. Concomitantly, developers are planning to add an additional 200 ha of green space inside of the city and 250 ha of green space on the outskirts of the city. According to the Healthy Urban Living 2040 Vision, the municipal actors aim to make Utrecht a 10-minute city with multiple city centres and an ample sustainable transport infrastructure²⁷.

UTRECHT FOOD SHARING LANDSCAPE

Quantity

Number of FSIs: **92** (8 Outside Utrecht and 85 inside Utrecht city boundaries)

Population per FSI: **3,931 inhabitants/FSI**

No. of translocal initiatives and online initiatives

We identified 7 translocal initiatives that have a physical or online presence in other cities and countries. These initiatives are either organizing cooking and eating activities like Buurtbuik which is active in four other Dutch cities or redistribution activities like TooGoodToGo which has an international presence. In total, **there are 24 FSIs without a physical location**. Some of these are interactive maps and directories (e.g. Fietsenvoormijneten, Burtkasjekaart, DumpsterDiving map, Buurtnatuur etc). Other initiatives operate mostly online with pop-up stalls at other FSIs locations in Utrecht and beyond (e.g. Groentetas, Rechstreeks, Local2Local). An interesting feature of the food sharing landscape in Utrecht is the existence of networks of FSIs, for example, Utrecht Natuurlijk is a network of community gardens that each operate at a physical location but coordinate their educational activities and funding applications jointly.

No. of initiatives with multiple locations within the city and what they share.

Food sharing activities can be found at **77 physical locations**, with 3 initiatives organizing activities at more than one location. For example, Buurtbuik is active at 4 locations in Utrecht, while Resto van Harte and Zorgterecht are present at 3 different locations. The main sharing activity of these initiatives is cooking and eating.

Initiatives outside Utrecht's administrative boundaries

Eight initiatives that are active in Utrecht city have their physical location outside the city boundaries. All of these initiatives are engaged in growing activities and three of them also do redistribution. For example, the farms and community supported agriculture gardens distribute their produce in Utrecht, while initiatives such as Fungi Factory collect waste, grow food and distribute the final product. The ZadGoed seed bank collects and redistributes seeds and knowledge from Utrecht and beyond.

Sector of sharing

FSIs were coded according to four sectors: collective growing, cooking and eating, redistributing and multifunctional. The analysis consisted of summing the number of initiatives based on three categories of food sharing: growing, cooking & eating, and redistributing. FSIs were deemed as multi-functional if more than one function (growing, cooking & eating, or redistributing) was full-filled. The percentage of FSIs was calculated by dividing the number of FSIs assigned a specific type out of the total number of initiatives. Hence, the sum of all percentages is higher than 100%. Furthermore, Table 1 and Figure 1 show the percentage of FSIs according to the type of activities performed with the mention that FSIs that engage in more than one food sharing activity was counted twice once according to the activities of cooking & eating, growing and/or redistributing and in the multifunctional category.

Table 1. Type of FSIs in Utrecht

Type of FSIs	N. of initiatives	% of initiatives
Cooking & Eating	44	48%
Growing	43	47%
Redistributing	26	28%
Multifunctional	20	22%

Figure 1. Percentages of the type of FSIs

The food sharing landscape (Table 1, Figure 1) in Utrecht shows that there is a prevalence of initiatives that focus on cooking and eating. Out of the total 92 initiatives, 48 % organize cooking and eating activities, 47% percent initiatives focus on growing and 28% percent are active in the food (re)distribution sector. More than 22% perform more than one food sharing activity. Cooking and eating initiatives serve an important social function in Utrecht. The municipality encourages residents with less financial means to participate in these activities through the U-pass. The U-pass offers discounts for sport activities and cultural activities, and includes dining events for people that earn below the social minimum wage. Most cooking and eating initiatives that perceive a fee for participation have a U-pass mediated fare.

While the focus of the community gardens and collective growing initiatives is primarily social cohesion rather than food production, some of these initiatives manage to sell produce in their farm shops and supply restaurants around Utrecht. For example, Voedseltuin Overvecht, Voedselbos Haarzuilens, and Koppelsteede City Farm work both with employees and volunteers. These growing initiatives serve a double function to the city, first, they have been integrated in the municipal greening strategy supporting biodiversity and other ecosystem goods and services, and second, they offer educational and leisure opportunities for residents.

Redistribution activities full-fill in two, distribution of food items that would be discarded (surplus food redistribution) and distribution of fresh produce sourced from the local producers (for example through community supported agriculture schemes or gleaning activities). Another redistribution activity that is less prevalent is redistribution of seeds (seed sharing) and organic waste (community composting).

institutional level, Utrecht municipality is involved in the development of Rijnvliet, an edible neighbourhood prototype in cooperation with MethaalCathedral and LeidscheRijn citizens.

Figure 3. Word Occurrence from FSIs Mission & Vision Statements

Furthermore, the goals of food-sharing initiatives were extrapolated from the activities of FSIs as they appear on their website and assigned pre-established codes: **environmental and/or social**. We observe that for FSIs in Utrecht, food sharing is a means to achieve broader social goals such as environmental education for youth and integration of people in a vulnerable situation including age, (dis)ability and migration background. From analysing the mission statements and activities, we observed that growing initiatives are often involved in offering educational activities, whereas the cooking & eating initiatives are particularly concerned with combating loneliness while also striving to offer affordable dignified meals for people in precarious situations. The environmental focus is most prevalent in initiatives undertaking redistribution and growing activities, with the latter having biodiversity protection as an underlying principle. More than half of FSIs adhere to multiple goals, often combining social and environmental ambitions.

Table 2. Focus of FSIs

Goal	Nr. of initiatives	% initiatives
Social	90	98%
Environmental	50	54%
Multifocus	61	66%

What is shared

FSIs in Utrecht share a wealth of things (termed elements), some with a physical composition like seeds, plants, meals and gardening tools or kitchen devices, while others are focused on sharing knowledge and skills or sites and spaces. We analysed the resultant data in two ways, first by the full range of elements being shared (Figure 4; Table 3) and then by broader categories of material stuff (Food; Meals; Plants; Seeds; Tools; Compost), skills (knowledge and skills) and spaces (land and kitchen) (Tables 4 & 5). To establish what is shared by FSIs in Utrecht the occurrence of each term in the three broad categories was counted and summed up. To establish the percentage of FSIs sharing an element we divided the sum of each term by number of initiatives. As presented in Table 5, FSIs can share more than one thing which means that the sum of percentages per category of things being shared will be greater than 100%.

Figure 4. What is Shared by elements (% of FSIs)

Table 3. What is shared by elements (% of FSIs)

What is shared?	% of total initiatives
Food	43%
Knowledge	38%
Meal	36%
Skills	30%
Land	26%
Plants	11%
Seeds	5%
Kitchen Space	7%
Compost	2%
Tool	0%
Kitchen Devices	0%

Food is the most shared item (here food refers to food products rather than prepared meals). In the category of FSIs that share food, the most prevalent examples are community gardens, followed by consumer-led purchasing groups (e.g. Voko) and online platforms that focus on direct selling of food items between farmers and consumers. The latter often provide additional knowledge on food preparation (recipes) and cooking workshops to the general public.

Knowledge is the second most shared resource by FSIs (Table3), this includes educational activities on growing and food preparation, foraging tours and various specialized workshops (e.g. food preservation workshops, and beekeeping).

Sharing meals is also an important part of the food-sharing landscape in Utrecht. From the 48% of initiatives that have been categorized as cooking and eating initiatives, more than 35 % focus on organizing shared meals on a weekly basis. In some cases, the ingredients come from food rescue activities as for example the Buurtbuik and Taste before you Waste dinners.

No FSIs explicitly focusing on sharing tools or kitchen devices were revealed through mapping. While we are aware that this type of sharing might be embedded in the day-to-day operations, very few FSIs in Utrecht are organized around sharing these items explicitly, or as their main activity.

Space is the least shared resource, FSIs that share space are often growing initiatives that offer to host other initiatives on their premise or community centres that run their cooking and eating, but also rent the kitchen to other similar initiatives. An example of a growing initiative that shares land is Stadtstuin Kanaalweg, which hosts 3 other growing initiatives on its premises. On the other hand, Buurtbuik is active at 4 locations in Utrecht which are mostly kitchens rented from the community centre. As in the case of Buurtbuik, it is very common for cooking and eating initiatives to operate at various locations on a rental basis.

In terms of capacity and sharing, we observed that half of initiatives share one thing, mostly materials goods (e.g. the stuff category of sharing), while 40% share more than one thing; often a combination of material products with skills and knowledge. Only 7% of FSIs in Utrecht manage to share across all three categories: stuff, space, knowledge & skills. Of the 92 initiatives identified in Utrecht, more than 78% share stuff (Table 4).

Table 4. What is shared by category stuff, space, & skills

What is shared?	% of total initiatives
Stuff: Food; Meals; Plants; Seeds; Tools; Compost	78%
Skills: Skills & Knowledge	43%
Space: Kitchen Space; Land	33%

Table 5. Number of elements shared by FSIs

What is shared?	No. of initiatives	% of initiatives
Share 1 thing	48	52%
Share 2 things	38	41%
Share 3 things	6	7%
Total Initiatives	92	100%

Modes of sharing

FSIs in Utrecht adopt a range of different modes of sharing from bartering and gifting to selling and collecting. Bartering involves exchange of goods or services, gifting implies no monetary exchange, whilst selling can be not-for-profit or for-profit. Collecting refers to activities such as gleaning or foraging. Data on approaches to sharing was taken from FSI profiles and allocated to one of these modes. Data on FSIs mode of sharing was counted using the occurrence of representative codes, percentages were further calculated by dividing the occurrence of terms by the total number of initiatives. As certain initiatives use more than one mode of sharing, the resulting statistics do not add up to 100%. Table 6 shows the percentage of total initiatives that operate using one or more transactional model. FSIs counted under the multimodal category use more than one transaction in their activities.

The preferred mode of sharing for Utrecht based initiatives (Table 6; Figure 5) is through selling, followed by gifting. It is common for FSIs that organize community meals to charge a symbolic fee for their services to cover basic costs such as staple ingredients and rent. For FSIs focused on growing, they may sell their produce in their community cafés and to other restaurants in Utrecht. Commonly, volunteers working in community gardens are often rewarded for their work with fresh produce. While these practices are largely informal, they often fall under the category of gifting or barter. Collecting is often an intermediate activity of FSIs active in (re)distribution. The collection of food items (e.g. from farms, fields, forests, gardens, skips) is then followed by gifting or selling to individuals or other initiatives. For example, Instock collects food that would otherwise be discarded and sells it to catering and restaurants through their online platform InstockMarket. Groenetas collects produce from local farmers and sells it to individual customers.

Table 6. Modes of sharing

How is it shared?	% of total initiatives
Selling	65%
Gifting	57%
Collecting	10%
Bartering	1%
Multimodal	29%

Figure 5. Mode of sharing used by FSIs (% FSIs)

Organisational structure of initiative

FSIs in Utrecht adopt a range of organisational structures to operationalise their activities. While the definition and legal categorisation of organisational structures is not uniform across Europe such organisational analysis is still useful to delineate splits between for-profit and not-for-profit FSIs both within Utrecht and between Utrecht and other locations. The organisational categories are based on, but also extend those established in the SHARECITY project²⁸.

The identification and calculation of percentages of FSIs organizational mode followed the same procedure as for the other coding categories. The occurrence of an organizational term was counted and divided by the total number of FSIs. As FSIs can operate under more than one organizational framework the percentages do not add up to 100%. For example, an initiative can be registered as a non-profit, but can run a social enterprise to finance the non-profit activities.

Figure 6. Sharing Organization (% of FSIs)

Table 7. Sharing Organization (% of FSIs)

Sharing Organization	% of total initiatives
Non-Profit	60%
Charity	53%
Network	16%
For-Profit	15%
Informal Network	8%
Association	3%
Social Enterprise	2%
Public Sector	1%
Cooperative	1%
Club	0%

In the context of Utrecht, the preferred *modus operandi* from a legal perspective is non-profit, with around 60% of FSIs being registered as non-profit foundations (*stichting*) or an association (*vereniging*). There is no significant difference between charitable organizations and foundations in the Dutch context, however, some FSIs have a clear charitable focus whereas other non-profits are operating as networks or associations. Whereas foundations have a broader societal goal, associations are formed by a group of

people that share similar ideas and values, as for example De Bickershof, a semi-public garden started and run by residents. Furthermore, some residents choose to organize at a grassroots level in informal networks, while they maintain an online presence through social media channels such as Facebook or Instagram, these groups are not legally registered under any particular legal entity and may not access funding.

For-profit and social enterprises make up around 20% of the FSIs. While social entrepreneurship is a rising trend in the food sector, there are very few social enterprises that qualify as food sharing initiatives. Most are focused on labour insertion and the circular economy sector. It is important to mention that some non-profits chose to run for-profit activities adjacent to the charitable activities as it's the case of care farms ('zorgborderijen').

Public sector initiatives and cooperatives remain minimal in Utrecht.

Technology

In order to be mapped the FSIs had to have a digital profile in the form of a website (or web application), Facebook, Twitter/X, or Instagram. Once identified FSIs were cross checked with the remaining social media platforms and via Google search engine to see if they had a presence or a website. FSIs are often active on more than one platform or have both a website and social media profiles. In the context of Utrecht, there were no significant number of FSIs operating other digital platforms, with the exception of TooGoodToGo that runs an app.

Table 8. ICT Presence FSIs

ICT use	Nr. of initiatives	%of total initiatives
Website	88	96%
Facebook	71	77%
Instagram	52	57%
Twitter/X	21	23%

An overwhelming majority of FSIs are running their own website or are part of other organisation's websites. The second preferred mode of communication is through Facebook with 77% of FSIs running a Facebook page or group. The least used mode of communication is Twitter/X with only 23% of FSIs having an online presence there.

SPATIAL ANALYSIS

The previous section provided an overview of the composition of FSIs within Utrecht. This section focuses on the geographical spread of FSIs. This spatial analysis is conducted only with the 74 FSIs that have a physical location within Utrecht city boundaries or its peri-urban area (as noted earlier there are 27 initiatives without a physical location in the municipality). There are also 3 cases where an FSI has multiple locations in the city and 8 FSIs operating outside the administrative boundary of Utrecht but within the commuting area delimited by the OECD. These are included in the following maps. A range of spatial analyses follow, including concentration of FSIs across Utrecht (and concentration by FSI sector); clustering of FSIs, and analysis of the location of FSIs relative to: population density, foreign populations, age, education, income and employment.

Utrecht is divided in 10 districts, 34 sub-districts, 111 neighborhoods and 194 sub-neighborhoods. Each district has a district office which oversees communication matters between residents and municipalities. Due to data availability and consistency across the three cities we perform the spatial analysis at the district level. The map below (Figure 7) shows the city of Utrecht and the municipal division by districts with the corresponding numbers and names. The geospatial analysis of FSIs in the reports has two different purposes: the first is to analyze where the FSIs function in the local neighborhoods as a social amenity or infrastructure, and second is to understand the concentration of FSIs and its relations with socio-economic characteristics of local districts.

Figure 7. Utrecht City Boundaries & Districts

Concentration Analysis

The analysis is built on a hexagonal grid of 500m of radius. The choice reflects the '15-minute city' concept, which is used to define and improve welfare facilities in urban planning, assuming the citizens have an average walking speed of 2 km/h on their daily movements to reach public services, green areas, public transport stops, supermarkets, and other essential services. To work on homogeneous areas, the territory of Utrecht was divided using a hexagonal tile grid of 500m of radius.

The number of FSIs existing in each tile were calculated which resulted in a concentration map, then categorized according to the sector of sharing (growing, cooking & eating, redistributing). Figure 8 provides an overview of the concentration of FSIs across Utrecht, which is represented by a one-scale choropleth map.

The concentration analysis is followed by a one-scale choropleth map showing the number of FSIs per tile and their sectorial categorization: cooking & eating (Figure 9), growing (Figure 10), surplus food redistribution (Figure 11). The visualization of FSIs by type was performed by filtering the field 'FSIs Type', resulting in thematic maps that show where growing, redistributing, and cooking/eating activities are concentrated (Figure 9-11) Finally, the maps offer the opportunity to develop a three-scale choropleth map, in which color mixing reveals the presence of the different categories (Figure 12).

Figure 8 below provides an overview of the concentration of FSIs across Utrecht. This map was constructed by Firstly, creating the hexagon grid at 500 m and counting the number of FSIs per hexagon. The colour shading reflects the concentration of FSIs per hexagonal shape. In the case of Utrecht, the highest concentration of FSIs is 2/500m, which is in crimson red.

Figure 8. Spatial Distribution FSIs Utrecht

The highest concentration of FSIs in Utrecht is in the Centre-East side (Districts 6 and adjacent Districts (1-5) of Utrecht City). The areas with the lowest concentration of FSIs is the West side (District 9,10).

Concentration Analysis: Growing

Figure 9. Concentration of FSIs which grow food in Utrecht

According to Figure 9, growing initiatives tend to be dispersed at the peripheries. With the highest concentration of growing initiatives in the East and North-East areas of the city (District 3, 4, 5) Community gardens and estates situated in District 10 and District 3 tend to cover a larger surface area compared to growing initiatives in the City Center (District 6 and around). The majority of FSIs that have their physical presence outside the Utrecht city boundaries classify as growing initiatives, except for one which qualifies as a redistribution initiative and a knowledge hub.

Concentration Analysis: Redistribution

Figure 10. Concentration of FSIs which redistribute food in Utrecht

As it can be observed in Figure 10, the food redistribution FSIs are concentrated on a North-South axis with little to no representation in the Western part of the city in District 9 and 10, as well as in the South-East part in District 5, 7 and 8.

Concentration Analysis: Cooking and Eating

Figure 11. Concentration of FSIs which organize cooking & eating in Utrecht

Cooking and eating initiatives are concentrated in the city center with the highest concentration in District 1 and District 5.

FSIs Clusterisation

Combining the FSI concentration maps from each sector reveals hot and cold spots for a variety of FSIs across Utrecht. Figure 12 below shows these features which were identified by ... overlapping the choropleth maps resulted from each FSIs type.

Figure 12. Cluster Map FSIs Utrecht

The map shows a sectorial approach in the distribution of FSIs. Cooking & eating initiatives are concentrated in the central area, despite being located in different districts, there is a palpable concentration of initiatives around District 6. Conversely, growing initiatives are dispersed across districts, yet these can be found towards the margins of the city boundaries. In terms of multifunctionality, based on this map the most common sectorial overlapping in between cooking and eating and redistribution (purple). District 3 seems to be the most diverse in terms of food sharing activities. District 10 is the least active with a rather homogenous typology of FSIs, mostly focused on growing. It is in District 10 that larger scale food growing activities take place, including food forestry projects (eg. Haarzuilens estate).

The concentration analysis provides a clear picture of the locational aspects of FSIs, however geography alone cannot explain why FSIs locate in particular places. The following analysis explores whether there may be correlations between location of FSIs and other socio-economic variables, including the location of FSIs relative to: population density, number of inhabitants per FSIs, foreign populations, ageing index, education level, average individual gross income, and unemployment rate. The analysis here is also done at the district level due to data availability.

Population density

Previous research has demonstrated that dense populations provide the network effects needed to support ICT-mediated sharing. With this in mind, population density per municipality was layered over the location of FSIs.

Figure 13. Population Density & Spatial Distribution of FSIs Utrecht

The North-South axis of Utrecht is densely populated, while the East-West areas show lower density values, with District 10 being the largest in terms of territory but the most sparsely populated. This reflects the historical development of the city, especially as the 2 most Western districts are the most recent addition to the urban reach of the city.

The occurrence of FSIs is concentrated in the Northern part of the city and corresponds with a high population density, specifically in Districts 1 to 4. In terms of FSIs concentration per population (Figure 13), District 3 records the highest number of initiatives (11), having 1 initiative per approximately 3,400 people. The districts with the lowest number of FSIs are located in the South of the city (ZuidWest-3 FSIs, Zuid-3 FSIs) and most Western Districts (LeidsjeRijn- 6 FSIs, Vleuten- De Meern- 4 FSIs). For example, in Utrecht ZuidWest the density is one FSI for approximately 13,200 people. The incidents of FSIs per inhabitant (Figure 9) partly confirms the relation between population density and FSIs concentration. Previously agricultural land, District 9 and 10 are the last two districts that were transferred to the jurisdiction of Utrecht Municipality and they are less densely populated than the rest of the districts.

Inhabitants per FSI

Figure 14. Inhabitants per FSIs Utrecht

Figure 15. Scatter Plot: Population Density & Inhabitants per FSIs

Based on Figure 14 & Figure 15 there is no evident correlation between population density and concentration of FSIs. Nevertheless, the most densely populated districts in Utrecht (2,4,6) show a similar occurrence of FSIs whereas the highest occurrence of FSIs happens in districts with median population density.

Foreign Population

Given the focus of many FSIs on supporting vulnerable or marginalised sections of society to integrate into communities, the concentration of foreign populations within municipalities was compared to the locational incidence of FSIs. Data was used which indicates the percentage (%) of population with 1st or 2nd generation migrant backgrounds in each district.

Figure 16. Percentage of the population with 1st or 2nd generation migrant backgrounds

Figure 17. Scatter Plot Inhabitants FSIs % of the population with 1st or 2nd generation migration backgrounds

The district with highest percentage of people with migration background is District 3 which coincidentally has the highest number of FSIs. On another hand, District 8 also records a high percentage of population with migration background, however the incidence of FSIs is among the lowest. As a result, we can conclude that there is no correlation between FSIs occurrence and migration background.

Ageing Index

The Ageing Index refers to the number of elderly population (aged 65 years and over) per 100 individuals younger than 15 years old in a specific population. Thus, the higher the index is, the older the population results. The Ageing Index is often used as a proxy for inferring economic dependency and locating vulnerable population groups based on age. It was used in this context to explore the location of FSIs relative to this index which is shown below, Figure 18.

Figure 18. Ageing Index Utrecht

For Utrecht the ageing index is relatively low, however with drastic variations of almost 200% between the lowest and highest number. The lower the value the youngest the population. The gap between the youngest and the oldest district in terms of population. There is a clear West-East divide with the youngest population being located in the Western part in Leidsche Rijn (District 9) and the oldest in the Binnenstad (District 6). Inferring a correlation between ageing index and FSIs concentration per inhabitant is difficult. However, taking into account the statistics that 53% of people aged 65 or older report feeling lonely², from the analysis of FSIs mission statements we observed that there is a focus of cooking & eating FSIs on elderly as for example Resto van Harte, PodiumOost, Zorgrecht, etc.

Education level

The location of FSIs was considered in relation to the percentage of the population above 15 years of age with at least a BSc.

Figure 19. FSI Percentage of Population over 15 years of age with a B Sc. Utrecht

Figure 20. Scatter Plot Inhabitants/FSIs & People with Higher education Level (%)

District 6 has the highest concentration of people with higher education diploma, while District 3 scores the lowest. As mentioned in the Utrecht City Profile, Utrecht city has the highest percentage of people with higher education in the Netherlands and it is home to 9 higher education institutions, out of which 20% of Utrecht city population are students. Another aspect to take in consideration is the location of the higher education university in central districts such as District 6. However, according to Figure 20 there is no significant correlation between location of FSIs and level of education.

Individual Average Gross Income

Figure 21 below shows the average yearly income per capita per district (€ thousands).

Figure 21. Average yearly income per capita Utrecht by district

In terms of yearly average income per capita, District 6 shows the highest income which correlates with the percentage of people with higher education. Nevertheless, in terms of FSIs concentration we observe that people in District 2&3 earn significantly less and also have a high concentration of FSIs per capita. Nevertheless, according to Figure 22 there is no clear correlation between income and occurrence of FSIs.

Figure 22. Scatter Plot Income Level & Inhabitants per FSI

Occupancy Rate

This map shows the percentage (%) of the population between the ages of 15-75 years who are in work or training by district.

Figure 23. Occupancy rate (%) Utrecht

Figure 24. Scatter Plot: FSIs concentration & Occupancy rate

As expected, based on the income data, districts where people have lower income correlates with the lower percentage of people formally employed. There are not major discrepancies between districts in term of occupancy rates, with the difference of 15% between the highest and lowest percentage. District 3 (Overvecht) shows the lowest percentage of employed people, followed by District 8, 7 and 2. While District 9 & 10 show high employment rate, the density of FSIs per capita is among the lowest. Nevertheless, according to Figure 24, occupancy rate is not conclusive for explaining the concentration of FSIs in a particular district.

CONCLUSION

This report documents the form, focus and location of FSIs across Utrecht and reveals a rich and diverse picture of the food sharing activities that operate within the municipality and its peri-urban area.

Looking at spatial and socio-economic indicators we can infer that districts who are generally scoring lowest on income, education level and occupancy rate have a higher incidence of FSIs per capita and also the most diverse in terms of FSIs types. For example, District 3 (Overvecht) has the highest concentration of FSIs per capita and in absolute numbers, and the district scores the lowest on income, education level & unemployment. Furthermore, the data shows that Overvecht is most concentrated in terms of people with migration background. However the data set is insufficient to draw precise trends in terms of FSIs occurrence.

While mapping is essential for locating practices within the city, it is also a necessary step for establishing any unevenness in distribution by different sectors of FSIs across the city. Various socio-economic variables were compared with the incidence of FSIs to explore whether any correlations emerged. No strong correlations were identified, although the limited availability of granular data and the low number of FSI data points restricts the level of statistical analysis that can be undertaken.

Further in-depth exploration of the drivers behind the establishment (or not) of particular FSIs in specific locations will be further explored through the CULTIVATE project running until December 2026.

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² <https://allecijfers.nl/gemeente/utrecht/>

³ <https://www.britannica.com/place/Randstad>

⁴ Central Bureau of Statistic, 2008, <https://www.cbs.nl/en-gb/news/2008/15/randstad-economy-fourth-largest-in-europe>

⁵ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1279533/gdp-per-capita-netherlands-by-province/>

⁶ <https://utrecht.incijfers.nl/dashboard/thema/werk-en-inkomen>

⁷ <https://www.utrechtregion.com/discover-utrecht-region/health/utrecht-science-park>

⁸ <https://www.maximaconsulting.com/newsroom/it-market-in-the-netherlands-2023>

⁹ Netherlands Institute for Multiparty Democracy & Instituut voor Publiek en Politiek, 2008, The Dutch Political System in a Nutshell, ISBN 978 90 64734298

¹⁰ <https://prodemos.nl/kennis/informatie-over-politiek/>

¹¹ <https://www.secuonline.nl/activiteit/ramadan-in-utrecht/>

¹² <https://www.provincie-utrecht.nl/english>

¹³ FAO, RUAF & WLU, 2018, ASSESSMENT AND PLANNING OF THE UTRECHT CITY REGION FOOD SYSTEM, ISBN 978-92-5-130869-1 (FAO)

¹⁴ <https://www.zorgboeren.nl/>

¹⁵ <https://www.utrechtnatuurlijk.nl/locaties/>

¹⁶ <https://www.voedselgeschiedenis.nl/en/foreign-foods-in-the-netherlands/>

¹⁷ <https://fairtradegemeenten.nl/>

¹⁸ <https://www.fao.org/in-action/food-for-cities-programme/news/detail/fr/c/381703/>

¹⁹ Utrecht and the Global Goals Voluntary Local Review, September 2023, Utrecht Municipality

<https://www.local2030.org/story/view/286>

²⁰ <https://volksgezondheidsmonitor.nl/gezondheid-en-leefstijl/voeding>

²¹ <https://sustainableurbandelta.com/sustainable-food-system-utrecht/>

²² <https://www.utrecht.nl/wonen-en-leven/bouwen/bouwprojecten/leidsche-rijn/buurt/rijnvlief/de-eetbare-woonbuurt/>

²³ <https://networknature.eu/casestudy/19453>

²⁴ Gemeente Utrecht, 2022, Sustainability Report <https://www.utrecht.nl/bestuur-en-organisatie/publicaties/onderzoek-en-cijfers/onderzoek-over-utrecht/duurzaamheidsverslag/>

²⁵ <https://www.utrecht.nl/city-of-utrecht/green-roofed-bus-shelters-in-utrecht/>

²⁶ <https://www.publicspace.org/the-prize/-/edition/2022/results>

²⁷ <https://omgevingsvisie.utrecht.nl/de-koers/ruimtelijke-strategie-utrecht-2040/>

²⁸ Davies, A. R., Edwards, F., Marovelli, B., Morrow, O., Rut, M., & Weymes, M. (2017). Making visible: Interrogating the performance of food sharing across 100 urban areas. *Geoforum*, 86, 136-149

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